

New species and records of Palaearctic, Afrotropical and Neotropical ichneumon wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)

ZOLTÁN VAS

*Hungarian Natural History Museum, Department of Zoology, Hymenoptera Collection,
H-1088 Budapest, Baross u. 13, Hungary. E-mail: vas.zoltan@nhmus.hu;
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1361-180X>*

Abstract – Palaearctic, Afrotropical and Neotropical species of the subfamilies Campopleginae, Acaenitinae, Cryptinae, Ophioninae and Tryphoninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) are treated. Regarding Campopleginae, two new species are described, namely *Hyposoter daeva* sp. nov. from Iran and *Nemeritis centurio* sp. nov. from Argentina, and the first records of *Bathyplectes incisus* Horstmann, 1974 and *B. quinqueangularis* (Ratzeburg, 1852) from Ukraine, *Campoletis yaga* Vas, 2024 from Argentina, *Casinaria pyreneator* Aubert, 1960, *Diadegma compunctellae* Horstmann, 2013, *D. longicaudatum* Horstmann, 1969, *D. nigrostigmaticum* Horstmann, 1969 and *D. semiclausum* (Hellén, 1949) from Hungary, *Hyposoter caedator* (Gravenhorst, 1829) and *H. didymator* (Thunberg, 1822) from Malta, and *H. orbator* (Gravenhorst, 1829) from Iran are reported. Regarding Acaenitinae, *Hieroceryx pseudoglomiger* Benoit, 1951 is reported for the first time from Ghana. Regarding Cryptinae, *Gabunia coerulea* Kriechbaumer, 1895 is also reported for the first time from Ghana. Regarding Ophioninae, *Enicospilus babaulti* (Seyrig, 1935) and *E. biimpressus* (Brullé, 1846) are reported for the first time from Guinea, and *Thyreodon boliviae* Morley, 1912 is reported for the first time from French Guiana. Regarding Tryphoninae, *Netelia caucasica* (Kokujev, 1899) is reported for the first time from Hungary. With four figures.

Key words – *Bathyplectes*, *Campoletis*, *Casinaria*, *Diadegma*, distribution, *Enicospilus*, *Gabunia*, *Hieroceryx*, *Hyposoter*, *Nemeritis*, *Netelia*, species description, taxonomy, *Thyreodon*

INTRODUCTION

Recently revealed results of the ongoing identification process of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) material in the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM) are presented in this paper: two new species of Campopleginae are described, namely *Hyposoter daeva* sp. nov. from Iran and *Nemeritis centurio* sp. nov. from Argentina.

New distributional records are reported for 17 ichneumon wasp species of the subfamilies Acaenitinae, Campopleginae, Cryptinae, Ophioninae, and Tryphoninae, regarding the Palaearctic, Afrotropical and Neotropical regions.

Taxonomy and nomenclature follow YU & HORSTMANN (1997) and YU *et al.* (2016). Morphological terminology follows GAULD (1984, 1991) and GAULD *et al.* (1997); however, in cases of wing veins the corresponding terminology of TOWNES (1969) is also used. Terminology of body surface sculpturing follows HARRIS (1979). Identifications were based on the works of CAMERON (1899, 1905, 1906), KRIEGER (1911), MORLEY (1912, 1913), VIERECK (1925), SONAN (1929), UCHIDA (1932), BENOIT (1951), HEDWIG (1957), HORSTMANN (1969, 1973, 1974, 1975, 1978, 1994, 2013), MOMOI (1970), TOWNES (1970*a, b*, 1971), DELRIO (1975), GUPTA & MAHESHWARY (1977), GAULD & MITCHELL (1978), GUPTA (1983, 1987), GAULD (1984), CHEN *et al.* (2017), RIEDEL (2018), VAS (2020, 2023*a, b*, 2024*a, b*), ARAUJO & DI GIOVANNI (2021), GALSWORTHY *et al.* (2023), and on examination of adequate type materials (at least from photos of scientific quality). The specimens were identified by the author using a Nikon SMZ645 stereoscopic microscope. Label data of primary type specimens are given verbatim, with additions and explanations in square brackets if necessary. Taxa are listed alphabetically according to their genus-group names.

TAXONOMY

Family: Ichneumonidae Latreille, 1802
Subfamily: Campopleginae Förster, 1869

Genus: *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869

Type species: *Limnerium parorgyiae* Viereck, 1910; designation by VIERECK (1910)
Diagnosis: TOWNES (1970*b*), GAULD (1984)

***Hyposoter daeva* sp. nov.**

(Figs 1–2)

Type material – Holotype: female, “Iran, Abu Ask, Elburgsgeb. [= Alborz Mts], 2000 m, 12.VIII.1960, leg. [J. F.] Klapperich”, specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155277; deposited in the Hymenoptera Collection of the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be distinguished from the known species of the genus by the following character states in combination: preapical flagellomeres longer than wide; inner eye orbits indented, distinctly convergent ventrad; mesopleuron densely and distinctly punctate on finely granulate to finely coriaceous background, with transverse and oblique rugae around the partly

smooth speculum; propodeum relatively elongate, especially posteriorly, convex in profile, coarsely rugose; propodeal carinae distinct, except median section of posterior transverse carina absent; area superomedia about as long as wide, posteriorly opened; areolet short-stalked, second recurrent vein ($2m-cu$) distal to middle of areolet; nervulus ($cu-a$) slightly postfurcal; tarsal claws with weak basal pecten; first tergite slender, slightly decurved close to its base, glymma virtually absent; second tergite almost $2\times$ as long as its apical width; posterior margin of seventh tergite slightly concave, not excised; flagellum brown, scapus almost entirely, pedicellus ventrally pale yellow; tegula ivory; metasoma orange except first to third tergites basally and sixth to seventh tergites medially dark; all coxae predominantly black; all trochanters and trochantelli entirely to predominantly ivory; hind femur and tibia orange, basal third of the latter externally ivory.

1

2

Figures 1–2. *Hyposoter daeva* sp. nov., 1 = holotype female, scale bar = 1 mm, 2 = propodeum (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Description – Female (Figs 1–2). Body length ca. 5.5 mm, fore wing length ca. 4 mm.

Head: Antenna with 31 flagellomeres; first flagellomere slender, ca. 4× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres distinctly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate with indistinct punctures, and with dense, short hairs. Ocular-ocellar distance 0.8× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.7× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits indented, distinctly convergent ventrad. Gena very short, very strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.3× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina distinctly before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, slightly impressed above toruli, median longitudinal carina absent. Face and clypeus weakly rugulose on granulate surface, both almost flat in profile; clypeus small, its apical margin weakly convex, weakly impressed, sharp. Malar space 0.6× as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible short, lower margin with a wide flange from base towards teeth, flange gradually narrowed before teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer and wider than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma distinctly and densely punctate on granulate to coriaceous background, more or less rugulose, mostly matt with dense, short hairs. Pronotum with transverse wrinkles on lower half, epomia relatively weak but discernible. Mesoscutum slightly longer than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and moderately deep. Scutellum moderately convex in profile, lateral carinae not developed. Mesopleuron densely and distinctly punctate on finely granulate to finely coriaceous background, with transverse and oblique rugae around speculum; speculum partly almost smooth and polished. Epicnemial carina complete, strong but not elevated, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it about its middle height. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated. Metanotum ca. 0.4× as long as scutellum, anteriorly with a pair of foveae. Metapleuron distinctly punctate, lower half rugulose, without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete, strong; propodeal spiracle oval, separated from pleural carina by about its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum relatively elongate, especially posteriorly, convex in profile, coarsely rugose. Propodeal carinae distinct, except median section of posterior transverse carina absent. Area basalis trapezoid, about as long as its anterior width, laterally weakly delimited. Area superomedia with irregular and transverse rugae, hexagonal, about as long as wide, behind costulae distinctly convergent, posteriorly opened. Area petiolaris with irregular and transverse rugae, medially slightly impressed, confluent with area superomedia, their junction distinct. Fore wing with short-stalked areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) distal to middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by about its width, weakly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted slightly above its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second

discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) vertical, straight, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate to coriaceous with weak, indistinct traces of punctures. Hind femur 5.7× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.6× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Hind tarsus without a midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs. Tarsal claws longer than arolium, basally weakly pectinate.

Metasoma: Compressed, very finely granulate to shagreened, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite very slender, 3.5× as long as its apical width, 1.3× as long as second tergite; petiolus slightly decurved close to its base; glymma virtually absent, a very shallow, narrow lateral impression in its place barely discernible; dorsomedian carina of first tergite indistinct. Second tergite almost 2× as long as its apical width; thyridium elongate oval, its distance from basal margin of tergite ca. 0.7× as long as its length. Posterior margin of sixth tergite straight, posterior margin of seventh tergite slightly concave, not excised. Ovipositor sheath shorter than apical depth of metasoma; ovipositor almost straight, dorsal preapical notch distinct.

Colour: Flagellum dark brown, scapus almost entirely and pedicellus ventrally pale yellow. Head black, palpi ivory, mandible pale yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula ivory. Metasoma: basal half of first tergite black, apical half orange; second tergite orange except its basal third and narrow posterior margin blackish; third tergite orange except basal quarter brown; fourth and fifth tergites entirely orange; following tergites orange with wide, brown patches medially. Wings hyaline, veins brown, pterostigma light brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae predominantly black, apically narrowly ivory; trochanters and trochantelli ivory; femora pale orange; tibiae internally pale orange, externally ivory; tarsi basally extensively ivory, otherwise yellowish, apical tarsomeres slightly darkened. Hind leg: coxa black, apically very narrowly yellowish; trochanter pale orange to ivory, basally narrowly brownish; trochantellus ivory; femur orange; tibia orange, basal third externally ivory; tarsus orange-brown to brown, extreme base of first tarsomere narrowly ivory.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – Iran.

Etymology – The specific epithet *daeva* is the name of the ancient Iranian (Zoroastrian) supernatural spirits or demons; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – Regarding its virtually absent glymma and the colouration of scapus, metasoma and legs, the new species is quite characteristic and cannot be confused with its congeners. By using the most complete identification key of the genus (GALSWORTHY *et al.* 2023), the new species keys out with *Hyposoter meridionellator* Aubert, 1965; this species is known from the Mediterranean area of Europe, and can be readily distinguished from the new species by its unusually short propodeum, somewhat flattened and straight

petiolus with sharp dorsal and ventral edges in profile, orange-brown (subbasally and apically brownish) hind tibia with only a small ivory spot at its extreme base, and more extensively dark basal tergites.

Genus: *Nemeritis* Holmgren, 1860

Type species: *Campoplex macrocentrus* Gravenhorst, 1829; designation by VIERECK (1914)

Diagnosis: TOWNES (1970*b*), HORSTMANN (1973, 1975, 1994)

***Nemeritis centurio* sp. nov.**

(Figs 3–4)

Type material – Holotype: female, “S. Arg. [= South Argentina] Rio Negro [Province] El Bolsón, [leg. Gy.] Topál, 6.III.[19]61 Nr. 301 [= 350 m, netted along Arroyo Negro]”, specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 156118. Paratypes: four females, same locality and collector as holotype but 21.III.1961 Nr. 342 [= 480 m, Mt. Piltriquitron, beaten from various trees and bushes, mainly *Lomatia*], 1.IV.1961 Nr. 370 [= 700 m, Mt. Piltriquitron, beaten from *Lomatia obliqua* bushes, near creek], 5.IV.1961 Nr. 375 [= 480 m, NW valley between forehill and Mt. Piltriquitron, singled in grassy forest clearing], 21.IV.1961 Nr. 408 [= 350 m, netted during and after dusk in chilly weather, along Arroyo Negro]; four males, same label data as holotype (two males), same locality and collector as holotype but 17.III.1961 Nr. 330 [= 350 m, beaten from blossoming *Myrceugenia exsupca* trees along Arroyo Negro], 2.V.1961 Nr. 432 [= 620 m, Mt. Piltriquitron, netted around solitary *Lomatia* bushes on sunny slope]; paratype specimens pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 156119–156126, respectively. The holotype and all paratypes are deposited in the Hymenoptera Collection of the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be distinguished from the known species of the genus by the following character states in combination: second flagellomere ca. 3× as long as its apical width; inner eye orbits parallel; gena in female 0.50–0.55×, in male 0.6–0.7× as long as eye width in dorsal view; clypeus granulate with a few, indistinct traces of punctures; mandibular teeth equal; mesopleuron granulate, impunctate, speculum mostly smooth; propodeum granulate; propodeal carinae distinct, except median sections of longitudinal carinae weakened or obsolescent, and median section of posterior transverse carina absent; area superomedia ca. 1.3–1.4× as long as wide, its lateral sides behind costulae subparallel to slightly convergent, posteriorly opened; area petiolaris lying almost in the same level as area superomedia; fore wing with

short-stalked areolet; second tergite in female ca. 1.5×, in male ca. 2× as long as its apical width; posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites widely concave in female; ovipositor sheath 1.0–1.1× as long as hind tibia, ovipositor almost straight; tegula yellow; metasoma blackish to dark brown; fore and middle coxae pale orange, hind coxa dark; hind femur reddish orange; hind tibia orange, basally and apically slightly darkened.

3

4

Figures 3–4. *Nemeritis centurio* sp. nov., 3 = holotype female, scale bar = 1 mm, 4 = propodeum (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Description – Female (Figs 1–2). Body length 3.5–4.2 mm, fore wing length 3.0–3.4 mm.

Head: Antenna with 26–27 flagellomeres; first flagellomere ca. 4×, second flagellomere ca. 3× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres quadrate to slightly transverse. Head transverse, matt, granulate without punctures, and with dense, moderately short hairs. Ocular-ocellar distance and distance between

lateral ocelli as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits barely indented, parallel. Gena in dorsal view $0.50\text{--}0.55\times$ as long as eye width, roundly narrowed behind eyes. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons weakly convex in profile, slightly impressed above toruli, median longitudinal carina absent. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile; clypeus entirely granulate with a few, indistinct traces of punctures, wide, its apical margin weakly convex, not impressed, moderately sharp. Malar space $0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible strong, relatively long, lower margin with a relatively wide carina from base towards teeth, carina gradually narrowed before teeth; mandibular teeth equal.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma matt, granulate, virtually impunctate, with dense, short hairs. Pronotum with transverse wrinkles on lower half, epomia distinct. Mesoscutum about as long as wide, convex in profile; notaulus only anteriorly developed, short, weak but discernible. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and deep. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carinae not developed. Mesopleuron granulate, impunctate; speculum mostly smooth, subpolished. Epicnemial carina complete, strong but not elevated, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it about its middle height. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated. Metanotum ca. $0.4\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete, distinct; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by $1.5\text{--}2.0\times$ its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum elongate, weakly convex in profile, entirely granulate. Propodeal carinae: lateromedian longitudinal carina distinct, except its median section (i.e., between anterior and posterior transverse carinae) more or less obsolescent; lateral longitudinal carina complete, discernible along its entire length, with slightly weakened medial section; anterior transverse carina (including costulae) strong, except its section between lateral longitudinal carina and pleural carina absent; posterior transverse carina strong, except its median section absent. Area basalis trapezoid (sometimes almost triangular), apically narrow, slightly longer than its anterior width. Area superomedia entirely granulate, matt, about hexagonal, ca. $1.3\text{--}1.4\times$ as long as wide, its lateral sides behind costulae subparallel to slightly convergent, posteriorly opened. Area petiolaris confluent with area superomedia, lying almost but not exactly in the same level as area superomedia, entirely granulate, matt, slightly impressed in the middle. Fore wing with short-stalked areolet, *3rs-m* present, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* relatively short, slightly curved towards wing margin; nervulus (*cu-a*) interstitial to slightly postfurcal, strongly inclivous, weakly curved; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a + Cu1b*) intercepted at about its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell almost right-angled. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a + abscissa of Cu1 between M and cu-a*) about vertical, weakly broken, intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*) at

about its lower third; discoidella spectral, proximally connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate. Hind femur 5.5–6.0× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. 0.5× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws thin and small, about as long as arolium, simple.

Metasoma: Compressed, finely granulate to shagreened, with dense, short hairs. First tergite conspicuously slender, 3.7–3.9× as long as its apical width, 1.1× as long as second tergite; glymma absent; dorsomedian carina of first tergite indistinct. Second tergite elongate, 1.50–1.55× as long as its apical width; thyridium small, rather narrowly elongate, its distance from basal margin of tergite 1.5–2.0× as long as its length. Posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites distinctly, widely concave, but not triangularly excised. Ovipositor sheath 1.0–1.1× as long as hind tibia; ovipositor almost straight, dorsal preapical notch distinct.

Colour: Antenna brown, scapus, pedicellus and basal flagellomeres narrowly yellowish brown at apices. Head black, palpi and mandible yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula yellow. Metasoma blackish to dark brown, posterior margin of second tergite very narrowly yellowish brown, posterior margins of following tergites often indistinctly, very narrowly paler than rest of tergites. Wings hyaline, veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs, including coxae, pale orange, apical tarsomeres slightly darkened. Hind leg: coxa blackish to dark brown; trochanter orange with brownish patches; trochantellus orange; femur reddish orange; tibia orange, basally and apically slightly darkened; tarsus orange-brown.

Male: Similar to female in all characters described above, except: antenna with 28 flagellomeres, first flagellomere ca. 3.5×, second flagellomere ca. 2.5× as long as its apical width, preapical flagellomeres longer than wide; gena longer than in female, in dorsal view 0.6–0.7× as long as eye width, weakly narrowed behind eyes; hind femur stouter than in female, 5× as long as high; metasoma more elongate than in female, first tergite 4.1–4.5×, second tergite 2.0–2.2× as long as its apical width; posterior margins of sixth and seventh tergites straight; parameres wide, apically rounded.

Distribution – Argentina.

Etymology – The specific epithet *centurio* reflects that this species is the 100th ichneumon wasp species described as new by the author; noun in apposition, ending not to be changed.

Remarks on identification – The new species can be reliably distinguished from any congeners based on the diagnosis above. Among the three *Nemeritis* species known to occur in the New World, *Nemeritis macrura* (Viereck, 1925) and *Nemeritis scaramozzinoi* Di Giovanni et Araujo, 2021 can be immediately distinguished from the new species by their much longer ovipositor sheaths and very different colourations (see ARAUJO & DI GIOVANNI 2021). The third species of the New World, *Nemeritis lativentris* Thomson, 1887, known both from the Nearctic and Western Palaearctic regions, is somewhat more similar,

however it can be readily distinguished from the new species by its significantly longer ovipositor sheath (1.6–1.7× as long as hind tibia), shiny area superomedia, brown fore and middle coxae, and as long as wide or only slightly longer than wide second tergite (HORSTMANN 1973, 1975, 1994, ARAUJO & DI GIOVANNI 2021).

NEW DISTRIBUTION RECORDS

Family: Ichneumonidae Latreille, 1802
Subfamily: Acaenitinae Förster, 1869

Hieroceryx pseudoglomiger Benoit, 1951

Material examined – Ghana: Volta Region, Bakpa, 6°49'55.96"N, 0°25'10.39"E, 487 m, 12.XI.2023, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Ghana. The species has been known from the Democratic Republic of Congo so far (YU *et al.* 2016).

Subfamily: Campopleginae Förster, 1869

Bathyplectes incisus Horstmann, 1974

Material examined – Ukraine: Mt. Hoverla, 1000 m, 17.VI.1997, leg. V. Ermolenko, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Ukraine. The species has been known from Germany, Poland, and Georgia so far (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Bathyplectes quinqueangularis (Ratzeburg, 1852)

Material examined – Ukraine: Mt. Hoverla, 1000 m, 17.VI.1997, leg. V. Ermolenko, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Ukraine. The species is widely distributed in the Palearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2023a).

Campoletis yaga Vas, 2024

Material examined – Argentina: Rio Negro, El Bolsón, 5.IV.1961, leg. Gy. Topál, 1♀; same locality and collector but 26.IV.1961, 1♀; Chubut, El Turbio, 19.XI.1961, leg Gy. Topál, 2♀; Chubut, El Hoyo, 14.II.1961, leg. Gy. Topál, 2♂.

Remarks – First records from Argentina. The species was recently described from Chile (VAS 2024b).

Casinaria pyreneator Aubert, 1960

Material examined – Hungary: Kőszeg, borospincék völgye [= valley of wine cellars], 6.V.1983, leg. I. Rozner, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018, 2022).

Diadegma compunctellae Horstmann, 2013

Material examined – Hungary: Noszvaj, Dóc-hegy [= Dóc Hill], 10.VI.2023, leg. V. Szőke & Z. Vas, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species has been known from the United Kingdom so far (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma longicaudatum Horstmann, 1969

Material examined – Hungary: Noszvaj, Dóc-hegy [= Dóc Hill], 30.VI.2023, leg. Gy. Dudás, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma nigrostigmaticum Horstmann, 1969

Material examined – Hungary: Kiskunhalas, along road no. 53 near Pirtó Sand Dunes, 13.V.2023, leg. V. Szőke & Z. Vas, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species has been known from Germany, France, Poland, and Bulgaria so far (YU *et al.* 2016).

Diadegma semiclausum (Hellén, 1949)

Material examined – Hungary: Páty, Mézeshegy, 19–27.V.2023, leg. V. Szőke & Z. Vas, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species is widely distributed in the Old World (YU *et al.* 2016).

Hyposoter caedator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Malta: Verdala Palace, 12–24.VI.2014, leg. D. Mifsud, 1♂.

Remarks – First record from Malta. The species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Hyposoter didymator (Thunberg, 1822)

Material examined – Malta: Marfa, 20.IV.2014, leg. T. Cassar, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Malta. The species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region, and also occurs in the Australasian region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Hyposoter orbator (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Iran: Alborz Mts, 2000 m, 12.VIII.1960, leg. [J. F.] Klapperich, 2♀.

Remarks – First record from Iran. The species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL *et al.* 2023).

Subfamily: Cryptinae Kirby, 1837

Gabunia coerulea Kriechbaumer, 1895

Material examined – Ghana: Oti Region, Kyabobo National Park, Laboum River Valley, waterfall trail hills 8°19'55.09"N, 0°34'54.20"E, 300–550 m, 11–20.XII.2022, leg. Sz. Sáfián & G. Győri, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Ghana. The species is widely distributed in the equatorial area of the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2022).

Subfamily: Ophioninae Shuckard, 1840

Enicospilus babaulti (Seyrig, 1935)

Material examined – Guinea: Coyah, 24.X.1967, leg. K. Ferencz, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Guinea. The species is widely distributed in the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2022).

Enicospilus biimpressus (Brullé, 1846)

Material examined – Guinea: Coyah, 6–7.I.1965, leg. K. Ferencz, 1♂.

Remarks – First record from Guinea. The species is widely distributed in the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2022).

Thyreodon boliviae Morley, 1912

Material examined – French Guiana: Regina region, Mt. Kaw, Patawa camp, 21–30.XI.2022, leg. Sz. Kiss, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from French Guiana. The species has been known from Bolivia and Peru so far (YU *et al.* 2016, LIMA 2019).

Subfamily: Tryphoninae Shuckard, 1840

Netelia caucasica (Kokujev, 1899)

Material examined – Hungary: Orfalu, csarabos [= heath], 46.8876°N, 16.2697°E, leg. G. Katona *et al.*, light trap, 1♀.

Remarks – First record from Hungary. The species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016).

*

Acknowledgements – Thanks are due to Anne Freitag and Marion Podolak (Musée cantonal de zoologie, Lausanne), Konstantin Samartsev (Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg), Maria Werner (Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde, Stuttgart) and James Hogan (Oxford University Museum of Natural History) for the scientific quality photos of type material deposited in their institutions; to Viktória Szöke (HNHM) for the drawings and post-image works; to all collectors of the material reported above (especially to Szabolcs Sáfián, Szilárd Kiss, and Gergely Katona); to the Hungarian Biodiversity Research Society for organising the Biodiversity Days and the Kiskunhalas-Pirtó Collecting Trip, as some of the reported species were collected during these occasions; to David Mifsud (University of Malta) for donating Maltese material to the HNHM in 2014; to Konstantin Samartsev and my colleagues from the Central Library of the HNHM for their help in obtaining some of the relevant literature. This paper was supported by the János Bolyai Research Scholarship of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

REFERENCES

- ARAUJO R. O. & DI GIOVANNI F. 2021: Description of the first species of *Nemeritis* Holmgren (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae) from the Southern Hemisphere, with a key to the New World species. – *Zootaxa* **5023**(2): 263–272.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5023.2.6>
- BENOIT P. L. G. 1951: Sur les genres éthiopiens *Gabunia* Kriechb., *Paracollyria* Cam. et *Hieroceryx* Tosq. (Hym. Ichneum. Pimpl.) spécialement au Congo belge. – *Annales de la Société Zoologique de Belgique* **82**: 93–106.
- CAMERON P. 1899: Hymenoptera Orientalia, or contributions to a knowledge of the Hymenoptera of the Oriental Zoological Region. Part VIII. The Hymenoptera of the Khasia Hills. First paper. – *Memoirs and Proceedings of the Manchester Literary and Philosophical Society* **43**(3): 1–220.
- CAMERON P. 1905: Descriptions of some new species of parasitic Hymenoptera, chiefly from the Sikkim Himalaya (Hym.). – *Zeitschrift für Systematische Hymenopterologie und Dipterologie* **5**: 278–283.
- CAMERON P. 1906: On the Tenthredinidae and parasitic Hymenoptera collected in Baluchistan by Major C. G. Nurse. Part II. – *Journal of the Bombay Natural History Society* **17**: 274–288.
- CHEN Y.-F., HUANG C.-L. & HSU Y.-F. 2017: DNA barcoding and morphological data reveal a new *Hyposoter* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Porizontinae) reared from a rare zygaenid moth *Artona flavipuncta* Hampson, 1900 in Taiwan. – *Zootaxa* **4337**(2): 279–287.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4337.2.6>
- DELRIO G. 1975: Révision des espèces ouest-paléarctiques du genre *Netelia* Gray (Hym., Ichneumonidae). Studi Sassaesi Sez. III. – *Annali della Facoltà di Agraria dell'Università di Sassari* **23**: 1–126.
- GALSWORTHY A., SHAW M. R. & HARALDSEIDE H. 2023: A key to European species of *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869 (Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae) with descriptions of 18 new species, and notes on all included species. – *Zootaxa* **5290**(1): 1–73.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5290.1.1>
- GAULD I. D. & MITCHELL P. A. 1978: *The taxonomy, distribution and host preferences of African parasitic wasps of the subfamily Ophioninae*. – CAB, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, 287 pp.
- GAULD I. D. 1984: *An introduction to the Ichneumonidae of Australia*. – British Museum (Natural History), London, 413 pp.
- GAULD I. D. 1991: The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 1. Introduction, keys to subfamilies, and keys to the species of the lower Pimpliform subfamilies Rhyssinae, Poemeniinae, Acaenitinae and Cyloceriinae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **47**: 1–589.
- GAULD I. D., WAHL D., BRADSHAW K., HANSON P. & WARD S. 1997: The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 2. Introduction and keys to species of the smaller subfamilies, Anomaloninae, Ctenopelmatinae, Diplazontinae, Lycorininae, Phrudinae, Tryphoninae (excluding *Netelia*) and Xoridinae, with an appendix on the Rhyssinae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **57**: 1–485.

- GUPTA V. K. & MAHESHWARY S. 1977: Ichneumonologia Orientalis, Part IV. The tribe Porizontini (=Campoplegini) (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Oriental Insects Monograph* 5: 1–267.
- GUPTA V. K. 1983: The Ichneumonid parasites associated with the gypsy moth (*Lymantria dispar*). – *Contributions to the American Entomological Institute* 19(7): 1–168.
- GUPTA V. K. 1987: The Ichneumonidae of the Indo-Australian area (Hymenoptera). Part 1. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 41: 1–597.
- HARRIS R. A. 1979: A glossary of surface sculpturing. – *Occasional Papers in Entomology* 28: 1–31.
- HEDWIG K. 1957: Ichneumoniden und Braconiden aus den Iran 1954 (Hymenoptera). – *Jahresbeft des Vereins für Vaterländische Naturkunde* 112(1): 103–117.
- HORSTMANN K. 1969: Typenrevision der europäischen Arten der Gattung *Diadegma* Förster (syn. *Angitia* Holmgren). – *Beiträge zur Entomologie* 19: 413–472.
- HORSTMANN K. 1973: Revision der westpaläarktischen Arten der Gattung *Nemeritis* Holmgren (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Opuscula Zoologica* 125: 1–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1127/entom.germ/1/1974/58>
- HORSTMANN K. 1974: Revision der westpaläarktischen Arten der Schlupfwespen-Gattungen *Bathyplectes* und *Biolyisia* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Entomologica Germanica* 1: 58–81.
<https://doi.org/10.1127/entom.germ/1/1974/58>
- HORSTMANN K. 1975: Neubearbeitung der Gattung *Nemeritis* Holmgren (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Polskie Pismo Entomologiczne* 45: 251–265.
- HORSTMANN K. 1978: Bemerkungen zur Systematik einiger Gattungen der Campopleginae. – *Mitteilungen Münchener Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 67: 65–83.
- HORSTMANN K. 1994: Nachtrag zur Revision der westpaläarktischen *Nemeritis*-Arten (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Campopleginae). – *Mitteilungen der Münchener Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 84: 79–90.
- HORSTMANN K. 2013: Revisionen von Schlupfwespen-Arten XVII (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Mitteilungen der Münchener Entomologischen Gesellschaft* 103: 113–126.
- KRIEGER R. 1911: Zoologische Ergebnisse der Expedition des Herrn G. Tessmann nach Sued-Kamerun und Spanisch-Guinea. Die Ichneumonidengattung *Gabunia* Kriechb. – *Mitteilungen aus dem Zoologischen Museum in Berlin* 5: 529–551.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mmzn.4830050312>
- LIMA A. R. 2019: *Cladistic analysis of Ophioninae Shuckard, 1840 (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae)*. – PhD dissertation, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Minas Gerais, 119 pp.
- MOMOI S. 1970: Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) of the Ryukyu Archipelago. – *Pacific Insects* 12(2): 327–399.
- MORLEY C. 1912: *A revision of the Ichneumonidae based on the collection in the British Museum (Natural History) with descriptions of new genera and species. Part I. Tribes Ophionides and Metopiides*. – British Museum, London, 88 pp.
- MORLEY C. 1913: *The fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma, Hymenoptera, Vol. 3. Ichneumonidae*. – British Museum, London, 531 pp.
- RIEDEL M. 2018: Revision of the Western Palearctic species of the genus *Casinarina* Holmgren (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Campopleginae). – *Linzer biologische Beiträge* 50(1): 687–716.

- RIEDEL M. 2022: New records of Darwin wasps (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) from Norway, with descriptions of three new species. – *Norwegian Journal of Entomology* **69**: 207–221.
- RIEDEL M., PÉNIGOT W., SCHWARZ M., DILLER E. H., JOHANSSON N. & JAPSHVILI G. 2023: Darwin wasps (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) of the Kintrishi National Park, Sakartvelo (Georgia), with descriptions of six new species. – *Linzer biologische Beiträge* **55**(1): 61–153.
- SONAN J. 1929: A few host-known Ichneumonidae found in Formosa (Hym.). – *Transactions of the Natural History Society of Formosa* **19**: 415–425.
- TOWNES H. 1969: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 1. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **11**: 1–300.
- TOWNES H. 1970a: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 2. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **12**: 1–507.
- TOWNES H. 1970b: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 3. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **13**: 1–307.
- TOWNES H. 1971: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 4. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* **17**: 1–372.
- UCHIDA T. 1932: H. Sauter's Formosa-Ausbeute. Ichneumonidae (Hym.). – *Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University* **33**: 133–222.
- VAS Z. 2020: Contributions to the taxonomy and biogeography of Nemeritis Holmgren (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae). – *Zootaxa* **4758**(3): 486–500.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4758.3.4>
- VAS Z. 2022: New species and new records of Afrotropical Ophioninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **83**: 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2022.83.1>
- VAS Z. 2023a: Contribution to the taxonomy, identification, and biogeography of the Palaearctic species of Bathyplectes Förster and Leptoperilissus Schmiedeknecht (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae). – *Zootaxa* **5270**(1): 105–114.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5270.1.5>
- VAS Z. 2023b: Still from Bíró's cornucopia: new species and new records of Campopleginae from Australia (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **84**: 63–97.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2023.84.63>
- VAS Z. 2024a: New species and new records of Oriental Campopleginae and Nesomesochorinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **85**: 61–79.
<https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2024.85.61>
- VAS Z. 2024b: New species of Campoletis Förster, 1869 from the Neotropical region (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae). – *Animal Taxonomy and Ecology* **70**(1): 22–29.
<https://doi.org/10.1556/1777.2024.12681>
- VIERECK H. L. 1910: Descriptions of new species of Ichneumon flies. – *Proceedings of the United States National Museum* **38**: 379–384.
<https://doi.org/10.5479/si.00963801.38-1754.379>
- VIERECK H. L. 1914: Type species of the genera of Ichneumon flies. – *United States National Museum Bulletin* **83**: 1–186.
<https://doi.org/10.5479/si.03629236.83.1>

- VIERECK H. L. 1925: A preliminary revision of the Campopleginae in the Canadian National Collection, Ottawa. – *Canadian Entomologist* 57: 176–181, 198–204, 223–228, 296–303. <https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent57296-12>
- YU D. S. & HORSTMANN K. 1997: *A catalogue of world Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera)*. – The American Entomological Institute, Gainesville, 1558 pp.
- YU D. S., VAN ACHTERBERG C. & HORSTMANN K. 2016: *Taxapad 2016, Ichneumonoidea 2015*. – Database on flash-drive. www.taxapad.com, Nepean, Ontario, Canada.

•••••

Új fürkészdarázsfajok és előfordulási adatok a palearktikus, afrotropikus és neotropikus faunarégiókból (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)

VAS ZOLTÁN

*Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum, Állattár, Hártýásszárnyúak gyűjteménye,
1088 Budapest, Baross u. 13., Magyarország. E-mail: vas.zoltan@nhmus.hu;
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1361-180X>*

Összefoglalás – Jelen közlemény palearktikus, afrotropikus és neotropikus fürkészdarázsak (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae, Acaenitinae, Cryptinae, Ophioninae és Tryphoninae) új fajait és előfordulási adatait tárgyalja. A Campopleginae alcsaládból két tudományra új fajt (*Hyposoter daeva* sp. nov. Iránból és *Nemeritis centurio* sp. nov. Argentínából) ír le a szerző, illetve az alábbi fajokat az adott ország faunájára újként közli: *Bathyplectes incisus* Horstmann, 1974 és *B. quinqueangularis* (Ratzeburg, 1852) Ukrajnából, *Campoletis yaga* Vas, 2024 Argentínából, *Casinaria pyreneator* Aubert, 1960, *Diadegma compunctellae* Horstmann, 2013, *D. longicaudatum* Horstmann, 1969, *D. nigrostigmaticum* Horstmann, 1969 és *D. semiclausum* (Hellén, 1949) Magyarországról, *Hyposoter caedator* (Gravenhorst, 1829) és *H. didymator* (Thunberg, 1822) Máltáról, *H. orbator* (Gravenhorst, 1829) Iránból. Első ghánai előfordulási adatait közli a *Hieroceryx pseudoglomiger* Benoit, 1951 (Acaenitinae) és *Gabunia coerulea* Kriechbaumer, 1895 (Cryptinae) fajoknak. Az Ophioninae alcsaládból az *Enicospilus babaulti* (Seyrig, 1935) és *E. biimpressus* (Brullé, 1846) fajokat elsőként jelzi Guineából, a *Thyreodon boliviae* Morley, 1912 fajt pedig Francia Guyana-ból. A Tryphoninae alcsaládba tartozó a *Netelia caucasica* (Kokujev, 1899) faj első magyarországi előfordulási adatait is közli. Négy ábrával.

Kulcsszavak – *Bathyplectes*, *Campoletis*, *Casinaria*, *Diadegma*, elterjedés, *Enicospilus*, fajleírás, *Gabunia*, *Hieroceryx*, *Hyposoter*, *Nemeritis*, *Netelia*, taxonómia, *Thyreodon*

ÁBRAMAGYARÁZAT

1–2. ábrák. *Hyposoter daeva* sp. nov., 1 = holotípus, oldalnézet, méretléc = 1 mm, 2 = áltorszelvény felülnézete (Vas Zoltán fotója, Szőke Viktória rajza)

3–4. ábrák. *Nemeritis centurio* sp. nov., 3 = holotípus, oldalnézet, méretléc = 1 mm, 4 = áltorszelvény felülnézete (Vas Zoltán fotója, Szőke Viktória rajza)